

ID	Estudo (título)	Referência
E1	Hidden skills that support phased and agile requirements engineering	Kovitz, 2003
E2	Balancing the human and the engineering factors in software development	Mnkandla & Dwolatzky, 2004
E3	The other skills of the software architect	Berenbach, 2008
E4	Influence of Human Factors in Software Quality and Productivity	Fernández-Sanz & Misra, 2011
E5	The 7 key factors to get successful results in the IT Development projects	Arias et al., 2012
E6	Self-Organizing Roles on Agile Software Development Teams	Hoda et al., 2013
E7	How do software developers experience team performance in Lean and Agile environments?	Fagerholm et al., 2014
E8	Investigating the skill gap between graduating students and industry expectations	Radermacher et al., 2014
E9	Agile Approach in the Project Management of the Czech Companies	Antlova, 2014
E10	Performance Alignment Work: How software developers experience the continuous adaptation of team performance in Lean and Agile environments	Fagerholm et al., 2015
E11	Personality traits of scrum roles in agile software development teams - a qualitative analysis	Baumgart et al., 2015
E12	Soft skills in scrum teams: A survey of the most valued to have by product owners and scrum masters	Matturro et al., 2015
E13	Human factors related challenges in software engineering: an industrial perspective	Lenberg et al., 2015
E14	Integrating human factors in information systems development: User centred and agile development approaches	Teixeira et al., 2016
E15	Understanding the Roles of the Manager in Agile Project Management	Shastri et al., 2017
E16	Análise de Soft Skills na Visão de Profissionais da Engenharia de Software	Lima & Porto, 2019
E17	Non-technical individual skills are weakly connected to the maturity of agile practices	Gren et al., 2018
E18	The Influence of Agile Practices on Performance in Software Engineering Teams: A Subgroup Perspective	Przybilla et al., 2018
E19	Comparing Computing Professionals' Perceptions of Importance of Skills and Knowledge on the Job and Coverage in Undergraduate Experiences	Exter et al., 2018
E20	Software tester, we want to hire you! an analysis of the demand for soft skills	Florea & Stray, 2018
E21	When Agile Means Staying: The Relationship between Agile Development Usage and Individual IT Professional Outcomes	Setor & Joseph, 2019
E22	Integrating Development and Operations in Cross-Functional Teams - Toward a DevOps Competency Model	Wiedemann et al., 2019
E23	Agile practices and motivation: A quantitative study with Brazilian software developers	Oliveira & França, 2019
E24	The Importance of Non-technical Skills in Agile Project Teams	Ćirić et al., 2020
E25	Non-cognitive Abilities of Exceptional Software Engineers: A Delphi Study	Groeneveld et al., 2021
E26	Preparing Future UX Professionals: Human Skills, Technical Skills, and Dispositions	Rose et al., 2020
E27	Evaluating the relationship of personality and teamwork quality in the context of agile software development	Gomes et al., 2020
E28	Requisite Skills Profile of Software Development Professionals for Startups	Mangiza & Brown, 2020
E29	Understanding Soft Skills as Cooperative Practices in Software Development: Reflections on an Internship Workplace	Miranda et al., 2021
E30	Exploring the Profiles of Software Testing Jobs in the United States	Kassab et al., 2021
E31	A case study on the perceptions of I.T. professionals during the transition from a traditional to an agile process model	Machado et al., 2021
E32	Exploring the Role of Creativity in Software Engineering	Groeneveld et al., 2021
E33	Requirements engineering challenges and practices in large-scale agile system development	Kasauli et al., 2021
E34	Do Agile Managed Information Systems Projects Fail Due to a Lack of Emotional Intelligence?	Luong et al., 2021

E35	Measures related to social and human factors that influence productivity in software development teams	Machuca-Villegas et al., 2021
E36	Improving Software Project Management by Applying Agile Methodologies: A Case Study	Quiña-Mera et al., 2021
E37	Improving Soft Skills in Agile Software Development by Team Leader Rotation	Libreros et al., 2021
E38	Mining the technical skills of open source developers	Montandon & Valente, 2022
E39	Motivators Influencing the Efficiency and Commitment of Employees of Agile Teams	Trzeciak & Banasik, 2022
E40	Exploring human factors of the agile software tester	Stray et al., 2022
E41	TACT: An instrument to assess the organizational climate of agile teams - A preliminary study	Dutra et al., 2022
E42	An opinion survey on skills of DevRel professionals	Cunha et al., 2022
E43	The essential competencies of software professionals: A unified competence framework	Assyne et al., 2022
E44	Employability skills: Profiling data scientists in the digital labour market	Smaldone et al., 2022
E45	Identificação de Soft Skills a partir da avaliação de anúncios de vagas em tecnologia da informação	Silva & Albuquerque, 2023
E46	Analisando as Soft Skills do ponto de vista dos profissionais de informática	Rocha & Albuquerque, 2023
E47	Human factors in developing automated vehicles: A requirements engineering perspective	Muhammad et al., 2023
E48	Software development teams: Factors influencing their productivity	Bollati et al., 2023
E49	Diversity and productivity in agile teams: Individual perceptions versus data	Motta & Braga Silva, 2023
E50	Soft and hard skills of software testing professionals: A comprehensive survey	Valle et al., 2023
E51	Using an instrument to assess trust, knowledge, learning, and motivation of agile teams	Dutra et al., 2023
E52	Soft skills of software developers: Exploring the pandemic's impact of COVID-19	Silva et al., 2023
E53	The influence of human aspects on requirements engineering-related activities: Software practitioners' perspective	Hidellaarachchi et al., 2023
E54	Soft skills required from software professionals in New Zealand	Galster et al., 2023
E55	On the roles of software testers: An exploratory study	Florea et al., 2023
E56	The impact of working from home on the success of Scrum projects: A multi-method study	Cucolaş & Russo, 2023
E57	Emotions online: Exploring knowledge workers' emotional labour in a digital context in an agile IT company	Pultz & Dupret, 2023
E58	Working with agile and crowd: Human factors identified from the industry	Qayyum et al., 2024
E59	Industry-academia and government collaboration to reduce gaps in software engineering: Applications for students and professionals in career transition	Marques Rocha et al., 2024
E60	Uncovering the skillsets required in computer science jobs using social network analysis	Maghsoudi, 2024
E61	Industry perceptions of the competencies needed by novice software tester	Hamid & Ikram, 2024
E62	Um estudo comparativo entre a visão de líderes e liderados sobre a importância de soft skills em desenvolvimento de software	Coelho et al., 2024
E63	The most in-demand soft skills for QA professionals in Brazil	Durelli et al., 2024
E64	Modeling competences in enterprise architecture: From knowledge, skills, and attitudes to organizational capabilities	Calhau et al., 2024
E65	Leaders, let's get agile! Observing agile leadership in successful digital transformation projects	Rialti & Filieri, 2024
E66	Do the project manager's soft skills foster knowledge sharing?	Avença et al., 2024
E67	An exploratory study on soft skills present in software positions in Cyprus: A quasi-replication study	Kapitsaki et al., 2024
E68	The roles, responsibilities, and skills of engineers in the era of microservices-based architectures	Michael Ayas et al., 2024

E69	'It's a spectrum': Exploring autonomy, competence, and relatedness in software development processes and tools	Wong et al., 2025
E70	Women security experts are not the enemy: A qualitative study on gender-related communication challenges	Yardim et al., 2025
E71	What makes a great software quality assurance engineer?	Silva Farias et al., 2025
E72	Habilidades colaborativas no mercado de TI: Uma investigação sobre requisitos de soft skills	Diniz et al., 2025
E73	Unveiling the skills and responsibilities of serverless practitioners: An empirical investigation	Hamza et al., 2025